

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: There is no denying, technology is part of the daily lives of children, teenagers, and adults. This impacts directly on the teacher and student relationship. Teachers who resist the inclusion of technology in their pedagogical practice end up stuck with outdated methods, which do not work in the same way. On the other hand, teachers who are able to take advantage of the benefits that technology can bring to the teaching and learning processes are able to act in a more attractive and innovative way with their students.

Key words: learning standards, curricula, provision, accelerate, artificial intelligence, dynamic, incorporate, collaborate, facilitate.

When Uzbekistan got its independence, first of all, our government began reforming economy of the country as economy is considered to be the basic foundation stone of the state. Uzbekistan began having good, friendly relationships with other foreign countries, our government had become ready to have equal, deep social, educational, economical corporation with a number of countries from the first years of independence which also led us to learn as many foreign languages as possible. The English language is learnt and taught by thousands of people round Uzbekistan.

As we know, on 19.05.2021 President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev signed a decree "On measures to bring the activities of popularization of foreign language learning in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level". The analysis of the current system of organizing language learning shows that learning standards, curricula and textbooks do not fully meet the current

requirements, particularly in the use of advanced information and media technologies. Education is mainly conducted in traditional methods. Further development of a variety of foreign languages learning at all levels of education; improving skills of teachers and provision of modern teaching materials are required.

According to the decree, foreign languages, mainly English, gradually throughout the country will be taught from the first year of schooling in the form of lesson-games and speaking games, continuing to learning the alphabet, reading and spelling in the second year. Also it is envisaged that university modules, especially in technical and international areas, will be offered in English and other foreign languages at higher education institutions. As we are future teachers it is compulsory for us to learn new teaching methods to make contribution to develop learners' outlook by using new technologies. Many technological resources offer to learn reports, helping faculty to identify, individually or collectively, where the subject matter is the most successful in which students need to study more.

Digital technologies have been changing the teaching and learning process the world over since they first appeared and then became an inalienable part of our daily life. In a modern society, the quality of education is affected either by the teacher's effective intervention or the education technologies or resources used in the foreign language classroom. Hence, digital technologies not only accelerate and significantly facilitate the educational process, but also make the learning process more interactive and cognitive.

Our future society will be dominated by artificial intelligence (AI) and advanced technology and automation, requiring the next generation of citizens entering the workforce to be technology savvy. This future, however, starts now, and ensuring high quality integration of technology in schools is required to help shape and build the digital society. The globalization of education has already necessitated the application of digital technologies. Online platforms were available for conducting classes, sharing resources, doing the assessment and

managing the day to day activities of academic institutions. However, the use of these platforms was proactive. The COVID-19 Pandemic has forced the institutes to adopt the online teaching mode to sustain the education system. Developed countries were well equipped to deal with this crisis. However, developing countries worked hard to meet this requirement. Digital technologies have emerged as the savior of education in this critical time This global crisis highlights the need to be internationally integrated into the education system. Digital technologies assist in developing abilities that will require students' professional performance, such as problem-solving, thinking structure creation, and process comprehension. They are also preparing for a more unpredictable and changing future in which technology will play a critical role. Students' acquired qualities and abilities will be essential to their professional success. Educational resources and digital tools help to improve the classroom atmosphere and make the teaching-learning process more compelling. Digital technology enables the storage of massive amounts of information in relatively small spaces. Large amounts of media, such as photos, music, videos, contact knowledge, and other reports can be carried around on small devices like mobile phones. Furthermore, they give each educational institution greater flexibility and customization of curriculum based on the requirements of each student. Children might become more engaged in learning if technology is used in the classroom. Because youngsters nowadays are pretty accustomed to the usage of electronic gadgets, incorporating them into schooling would undoubtedly assist in piquing their interest and enhancing their involvement levels. Integrating technology into education provides students with an engaging learning experience, allowing them to remain more interested in the subject without being distracted. The utilization of projectors, computers, and other cutting-edge technical gear in the classroom may make studying fascinating and entertaining for students. Student learning can become more dynamic and engaging by establishing tasks in class that incorporate technology resources, oral presentations, and group participation. Participation can extend beyond verbal communication as well.

Using computers and other devices in conjunction with digital tools allows students to play a more proactive role and be at the center of the process. The instructor becomes a guide in this process and can approve learning efficiency. Using the myriad of digital resources, learners may download the required information or upload their content. The web 2.0 technologies facilitate learners to generate content, collaborate with others, assess each other work and move toward co-learning. Digital technologies make it easy to use classroom tactics like gamification or approaches like flipped classrooms that optimize learning. Learning landscapes have evolved as a didactic tool that mixes several techniques and enables distinct itineraries to be presented to each student[1:p.83-92]. Technology makes the instruction more inspiring and meaningful. There is a strong consensus that digital technology can improve teaching and learning by motivating students with engaging, interactive, and fun learning environments. For example, digital technology offers new avenues of meaningful communication and collaboration between teachers and students. Communication, social networking, collaboration, content management, and access to analytics data, as well as staff and customer satisfaction, can all benefit from digital technology.

According to Tomlinson, differentiated instruction is a flexible approach to teaching in which the teacher plans and carries out varied approaches to the content, the process, or the product in anticipation of and in response to student differences in readiness, interests, and learning need.[2;p39-56]

Teachers direct their attention on methods and developments that guarantee successful learning for diverse students. Tomlinson also mentions that “Differentiated instruction properly implies the development of classrooms in which students sometimes exercise varied learning options, work at different paces, and are assessed with a variety of indicators appropriate to their interests and needs. It involves the enhancements of content, teaching, and evaluation to meet the needs of distinctive learners.”[3:p. 78]

One more successful approach of English language teaching that can incorporate with digital technology is Project Based Learning. Project Based Learning is a teaching methods in which students gain knowledge and skills by working for an extended period of time to investigate and respond to a complex question, problem, or challenge. There are several essential elements of PBL.

- Significant Content that focus of the project on teaching students important knowledge and skills, derived from standards and key concepts at the heart of academic subjects.
- Students build competencies valuable for today's world, such as problem solving, critical thinking, problem solving, collaboration, communication, and creativity, innovation, which are clearly taught and assessed.
- In-Depth Inquiry - Students are engaged in an extended, rigorous process of asking questions, using resources, and developing answers.
- Project work is focused by an undefined question that students understand and find interesting, which captures their task or frames their exploration.
- Students see the need to gain knowledge, understand concepts, and apply skills in order to answer the driving question and create project products, beginning with an entry event that generates interest and curiosity.
- Students are allowed to make some choices about the products to be created, how they work, and how they use their time, guided by the teacher and depending on age level and PBL experience.
- The project includes processes for students to give and receive feedback on the quality of their work, leading them to make revisions or conduct further inquiry. Students present their work to other people, beyond their classmates and teacher.

In conclusion, at present time it is important to use digital technology in classroom as our life is fully connected with a modern technology and we can't change or we cannot reject digital technology in the English classroom nowadays,

that is why the whole class should be related to digital technology. Besides younger generation of modern time are also interested in digital technology if you conduct a class with the help of technology equipment learners can be more interested in learning a second language rather than just working with textbooks.

Taking this into consideration each second language teacher of present time must be acquainted with digital technology to conduct classes.

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